



(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) –Scheme of Plasma Focus setup and sample holder for the deposition of particles on glass substrates under the shock-wave effect of plasma jet on metal foils: 1 - sample holder rod; 2 - metal disk that is 5 mm thick with holes 15 mm in diameter; 3 - clamping metal plate; 4 - glass plate; 5 - soft pads; 6 - metal diaphragm with a hole with a diameter of 15 mm; 7 - metal foil; 8 - cathode; 9 – anode; 10 – photo in visible light of the plasma jet with the time resolution 5 ns. (b) – electrodes of Plasma Focus setup.